

Determinants of Home Economics Career Pursuance: Application of Logistic Regression Approach

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to determine which domains of socio-demographic profile and determinants of home economics career significantly influence students' home economics career pursuance. This study used the descriptive-predictive research design. The respondents of this study were 82 junior high school students from Proper Ned National High School, Lake Sebu District, South Cotabato Division. The researcher used the Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) in selecting the respondents. The gathered data were analyzed and interpreted by using the statistical tools frequency and percentage, mean, Logistic, Regression Analysis. The results revealed that on the socio-demographic profile of the students, the findings revealed a relatively balanced distribution between male and female respondents. Meanwhile, most of the students were within the mid- to late-teenage range. Moreover, on the level of determinants of a Home Economics career, results indicated that social influence and self-efficacy were the most evident factors, while classroom-based and outdoor activities were moderately observed. Further, it was found that more students expressed willingness to pursue this path compared to those who did not. Lastly, on the influence of socio-demographic profile and determinants on students' career decision, the analysis confirmed that self-efficacy plays a significant role in predicting students' likelihood of pursuing a Home Economics career. Thus, it is recommended that Department of Education should enhance the implementation of career guidance programs that are responsive to the developmental stage of learners.

KEY WORDS

1. Home economics 2. career pursuance 3. determinants

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1. Introduction

Globally, the demand for home economics graduates is very high. Many countries in the world face the task of recruiting more individuals into home economics industries. Home economics, which was historically based on domestic science and household management, has expanded to include a wide range of professions such as nutrition and culinary arts, as well as family and consumer sciences education, interior design and textiles. However, students' interest in home economics careers is declining. Several studies reported a decline in student engagement with home economics and subsequent choices to pursue home economics-related careers. Despite their long history and significance in modern society, home economics jobs are occasionally disregarded or misunderstood. According to Waxman and Sahin (2021), although there are quite a few studies on how students choose their careers in general, the spe-

cific research on home economics career aspirations is somehow limited. Also, while there is a substantial amount of research conducted on students' home economics persistence and career selection in college-level experiences, there is a research gap on the development of home economics interest in high school.

With this, the researcher is prompted to pursue this study since the factors on students' home economics pursuance are not yet fully explored. The results of this study will guide students, parents, and even teachers to encourage learners to pursue home economics in the future since graduates of this kind of career are helpful in building society and can contribute to building the country's economy. Furthermore, understanding these factors can help educational institutions design more effective programs that align with students' interests and needs. Ultimately, this study aims to promote awareness and appreciation of home economics as a valuable academic and career path.

The study pursued answers to the ensuing objectives: a.) to determine the socio-demographic profile of the students in terms of gender and age b.) to determine the level of determinants of home economics career in terms of activities in the classroom, outdoor classroom activities, social influence, and self-efficacy, c.) to determine the level of home economics career pursuance of students, and d.) to determine which domains of socio-demographic profiles and determinants of home economics

career significantly influence home economics career pursuance of students.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypothesis was tested: a.) None of the domains in Socio-demographic profile and determinants of home economics career significantly influence home economics career pursuance of students.

Studying students' pursuit of home economics careers was important for improving education, workforce readiness, and societal growth. School heads benefited by using insights to allocate resources more effectively, improving the quality of home economics education. Teachers tailored instruction to better match students' interests and career goals, enhancing engagement and learning outcomes. Students gained access to creative, innovative career paths with global opportunities and transferable skills. Overall, the study supported more informed decision-making and inspired future professionals in the field.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—Figure 1 displayed the conceptual framework showing the variables of the study. It showed the interaction between the independent variables and the dependent variable of the study. The independent variables were activities in the classroom, outdoor classroom activities, social influence, and self-efficacy. On the other hand, the dependent variable of the study was the home economics career pursuance of students.

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a descriptive-predictive research design. The descriptive part helped determine the levels of classroom activities, outdoor activities, social influence, and self-efficacy among students.

The predictive aspect, using logistic regression, examined how these factors influenced students' decisions to pursue home economics careers. Logistic regression was suitable due to the binary nature of the dependent variable.

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This design allowed the researchers to both describe current trends and predict future outcomes based on observed patterns. It provided a comprehensive approach to understanding the relationship between student experiences and career decision-making.

2.2. *Ethical Consideration*—Ethical standards set by RMC’s Research Ethics Committee were strictly followed. These included principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and protection of participants from harm. Participation was voluntary, and students could withdraw anytime without consequences. The study emphasized fairness, transparency, and the privacy of participants’ data. All data collected were securely stored and accessed only by authorized personnel to maintain privacy. Additionally, any findings reported were anonymized to prevent identification of individual participants.

2.3. *Research Respondents*—Ethical standards set by RMC’s Research Ethics Committee were strictly followed. These included principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Permission to conduct the study was obtained from rel-

evant authorities, followed by coordination with school principals. The instrument was validated protection of participants from harm. Participation was voluntary, and students could withdraw anytime without consequences. The study emphasized fairness, transparency, and the privacy of participants’ data. All data collected were securely stored and accessed only by authorized personnel to maintain privacy. Additionally, any findings reported were anonymized to prevent identification of individual participants.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—A validated, adapted survey questionnaire from Halim et al. (2023) was used to measure determinants such as classroom and outdoor activities, social influence, and self-efficacy. The questionnaire included 16 items, revised for relevance and clarity. A 5-point Likert scale assessed the frequency of behaviors and perceptions. The instrument underwent expert validation and pilot testing for reliability. The pilot test confirmed the tool’s internal consistency, yielding a strong Cronbach’s alpha of 0.87. This ensured the instrument’s suitability for accurately capturing the targeted behavioral and perceptual factors.

by experts and pilot-tested with students outside the study sample. Survey distribution used both online and face-to-face methods, including dropboxes. Responses were retrieved securely, and incomplete data were reviewed and handled accordingly. To ensure ethical compli-

ance, participants were informed of the study's purpose and gave their informed consent before taking part. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the data collection and analysis process.

2.6. Data Analysis—Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used for descriptive analysis. Logistic regression was applied to determine the

predictive influence of socio-demographics and other factors on career choice. These methods allowed the researcher to explore trends and relationships. Data were carefully analyzed to draw meaningful, objective conclusions.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results and discussion of the study. The presentation began with a descriptive analysis of the socio-demographic profile of the students in terms of gender and age, followed by the level of determinants of home economics career in terms of activities in the classroom, outdoor classroom activities, social influence, and self-efficacy. It concluded with a discussion of the logistic regression analysis of the gathered data on the influence of the students' socio-demographic profiles and the determinants of home economics careers on their pursuance of a home economics career.

3.1. Socio-Demographic Profile of The Students—Table 1 displayed the data on the socio-demographic profile of the students. The frequency and percentage scores for each variable were presented in both tabular and textual representations. The results revealed that slightly more than half of the respondents were female, with 44 students representing 53.66% of the total. Male students accounted for 38 respondents or 46.34%. The table also highlighted the distribution of students across different grade

levels and age groups, providing a comprehensive overview of the sample characteristics.

In terms of age, the largest group of respondents were 17 years old, with 24 students comprising 29.27% of the total. This was followed by those aged 18 and above, with 20 respondents or 24.39%. Students aged 15 and 16 each accounted for 19 respondents, representing 23.17% respectively. These findings suggest a relatively balanced gender distribution and a concentration of students in the mid- to late-teenage years within the respondent group.

3.2. Level of Determinants of Home Economics Career—Table 2 showed the level of the determinants of a Home Economics career, which were measured by four (4) indicators, namely: (1) activities in the classroom, (2) outdoor classroom activities, (3) social influence, and (4) self-efficacy. The mean ratings

of these indicators are as follows: (1) activities in the classroom (3.24), which was described as Moderate; (2) outdoor classroom activities (3.36), which was described as Moderate; (3) social influence (3.80), which was described as High; and (4) self-efficacy (3.61), which was described as High. The four indicators/domains

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of the Students

Socio-demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender (N = 82)		
Male	38	46.34%
Female	44	53.66%
Overall	82	100%
Age (N = 82)		
15 years old	19	23.17%
16 years old	19	23.17%
17 years old	24	29.27%
18 and above	20	24.39%
Overall	82	100%

on the level of determinants of a Home Economics career generated an overall mean rating of 3.50, described as High, which indicates that

the determinants of a Home Economics career were oftentimes manifested in school.

Table 2. Level of Determinants of Home Economics Career

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Activities in the Classroom	3.24	Moderate
2	Outdoor Classroom Activities	3.36	Moderate
3	Social Influence	3.80	High
4	Self-Efficacy	3.61	High
	Overall Mean	3.50	High

Legend: 1.00–1.79: Very Low, 1.80–2.59: Low, 2.60–3.39: Moderate, 3.40–4.19: High, 4.20–5.00: Very High

3.3. Level Of Home Economics Career Pursuance of Students —Table 3 presents the profile of students who would like to pursue a Home Economics career. This is classified into two categories: will pursue and will not pursue. The results reveal a higher number of respondents who intend to pursue a career in Home Economics, accounting for 56.70 percent or 51 students. On the other hand, 43.30 percent or 39

respondents indicated that they will not pursue a Home Economics career. These results suggest that more students are inclined toward pursuing a career in Home Economics. This inclination may reflect the students’ positive perceptions of the field or their confidence in their related skills and interests. Further analysis could explore the factors influencing these career choices to better support student decision-making.

Table 3. Home Economics Career Pursuance of Students

Home Economics Career Pursuance	Frequency	Percentage
Will Pursue	47	57.32%
Will Not Pursue	35	42.68%
Overall	82	100%

3.4. *Domains Of Socio-Demographic Profiles and Determinants of Home Economics Career That Significantly Influence Home Economics Career Pursuance of Students*—Table 4 presents the influence of socio-demographic profile and determinants on students’ pursuance of a Home Economics career. The results showed that students’ self-efficacy obtained an exponentiated beta of .004 with a p-value of .042. This means that for every increase in self-efficacy, students are .004 times more likely to pursue a career in Home Economics. Furthermore, the result indicates that self-efficacy significantly influences students’ decision to pursue a Home Economics career. This leads to the

rejection of the null hypothesis.

Additionally, the Omnibus Test recorded a Chi-square value of 76.132 with a p-value of .000, indicating significance. This suggests that the model with predictor variables performs better than the null model. Moreover, the Cox and Snell and Nagelkerke R-squared values were .571 and .766, respectively. These values represent the variance explained by the predictor variables in relation to students’ pursuance of a Home Economics career. The high R-squared values indicate a strong explanatory power of the model in predicting students’ career choices. This reinforces the relevance of the selected predictor variables in understanding factors influencing students’ decisions.

Table 4. Domains of Socio-Demographic Profiles and Determinants of Home Economics Career That Significantly Influence Home Economics Career Pursuance of Students

Determinants	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Constant	—	—	—	—	—
Gender	22.888	0.454	0.000	0.997	0.335
Age	1.093	0.687	4.554	0.208	2.982
Activities in the Classroom	0.386	0.883	0.191	0.662	1.470
Outdoor Classroom Activities	2.256	2.115	1.138	0.286	9.543
Social Influence	2.139	2.087	1.050	0.305	8.488
Self-Efficacy	-5.610	3.008	3.477	0.042*	0.004
Model Statistics					
Chi-square	76.132 ($p = .000$)*				
Cox and Snell R ²	.571				
Nagelkerke R ²	.766				

*Significant at $p < .05$

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the socio-demographic profile of the students in terms of: (1) gender, and (2) age. Also, to determine level of determinants of home economics career in terms of: (1) activities in the classroom, (2) outdoor classroom activities, (3) social influence, and (4) self-efficacy. Further, it aimed to determine the level of home economics career pursuance of students. In addition, data were gone through psychometric analysis to draw out the domains of socio-demographic profiles and determinants of home economics career significantly influence home economics career pursuance of students. The following were the significant findings:

4.2. Conclusions—On the socio-demographic profile of students, it can be concluded that the respondents represented a balanced distribution in terms of gender and were predominantly within the age group typically associated with career decision-making. This demographic pattern indicates that students are at a developmental stage where they are beginning to form concrete ideas about their future careers. Such a profile suggests an opportune time for schools to implement career guidance programs that address the unique needs and influences relevant to this age group. This conclusion is best supported by the Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT), which considers both personal and contextual factors—such as age, sex, and learning experiences—as influential variables in shaping career interests and choices.

On the level of determinants of a Home Economics career, the results lead to the conclusion that social influence and self-efficacy are the most prominent factors affecting students' inclination toward the field. Although classroom and outdoor activities played a moderate role, it is evident that students are more driven

by the encouragement they receive from their environment and their belief in their personal capability. This highlights the importance of reinforcing supportive environments and fostering self-confidence among students to promote interest in vocational career paths like Home Economics. This aligns strongly with the Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT), which emphasizes the roles of self-efficacy and social influence as key cognitive-person variables that guide students' career development.

On the intention of students to pursue a Home Economics career, it can be concluded that a greater number of students are inclined to consider this field as a viable career option. This shows that Home Economics remains a relevant and appealing choice for many learners when supported by appropriate educational exposure and social reinforcement. The positive inclination observed suggests that with sustained encouragement and improved program delivery, more students may be motivated to pursue this pathway. This conclusion is best supported by the Expectancy-Value Theory, which explains that students are more likely to pursue a career they both value and expect to succeed in—indicating that students who find purpose and utility in Home Economics are more motivated to follow it.

On the influence of socio-demographic profile and determinants on career pursuit, the study concludes that among the different predictors, self-efficacy significantly affects students' decision to pursue a Home Economics career. The model used also proved to be statistically significant, confirming the combined effect of the factors measured. This means that enhancing students' confidence in their own skills can lead to more definitive and positive career choices. The conclusion supports the importance of targeted interventions that build students' belief in

their abilities while also considering their social context. This is well aligned with the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) theory grounded in Constructivism, which promotes learner autonomy and continuous development of self-efficacy by allowing students to explore and apply knowledge in meaningful, real-world contexts.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The Department of Education should strengthen career guidance programs that introduce vocational options like Home Economics through curriculum integration and industry partnerships. School heads are encouraged to support student interest in

this field by organizing relevant activities and collaborating with local enterprises. Teachers should use strategies that boost student confidence and integrate real-life applications to enhance engagement in Home Economics. Students are encouraged to explore their interests through active participation in academic and extracurricular activities to make informed career choices. Future researchers should examine the long-term effects of self-efficacy and social influence on career decisions, and consider broader samples and mixed methods for deeper insights.

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